

Microwave-induced hafnium(IV) chloride-mediated self-coupling of D-glycal: A simple route to C-(1-3) disaccharides

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A simple microwave-induced method for the coupling of two glucals to a novel C-disaccharide is realized through hafnium tetrachloride-catalyzed reaction.

Keywords: Hafnium tetrachloride, glucal, coupling, C-disaccharide.

Introduction

Lewis acid-mediated reaction of glycal with suitable glycosyl acceptor-the Ferrier type of rearrangement has been extensively used in the synthesis of 2,3-unsaturated glycosides¹. In the past few years a considerable effort has been made towards the synthesis of C-glycosides. Because of its interesting chemistry and versatile synthetic utility, C-glycosides are used to the development of novel materials, surfactants and biologically active molecules. C-glycoside analogous of the O-glycosides is used as intermediates for the synthesis of numerous medicinally active molecules². Several methodologies have been developed for the synthesis of C-glycosides³. Ferrier rearrangement is one of the most powerful techniques which describe Lewis acid⁴ or Bronsted acid-catalyzed reaction of glycal⁵. Numerous C-nucleophilic glycosyl acceptors, allyl silane⁶, silyl acetylene⁷ and organo zinc⁸ have emerged as powerful reagents for the preparation of glycosides. Glycosyl cyanide and azide also draw a considerable attention as the azide and cyanide functional groups can be transformed into a variety of other groups which can readily utilized in various organic transformations.

In view of our continued efforts, our group has developed numerous novel methods for synthesizing glycosides through

Ferrier rearrangement⁹. We herein aim to synthesize various glycosyl nitrile from glucal via carbon Ferrier rearrangement of glycal and silyl nitrile using hafnium(IV) chloride as potential glycosyl activator under microwave irradiation method. Hafnium tetrachloride (HTC) is a versatile and highly efficient catalyst, which synthetic efficiency has been proved in literature in many reactions¹⁰. To the best of our literature survey the use of hafnium tetrachloride in carbohydrate chemistry is not well explored despite of its very strong catalytic profiles. Microwave-induced hafnium tetrachloride-catalyzed reactions are not known.

The unique catalytic properties and convenience of using this catalyst prompt us to explore its utility in carbon Ferrier rearrangement which is not established in chemistry. During the course of these investigations, we explored the reaction of a glucal derived from glucose and trimethyl silyl cyanide as glycosyl acceptor in the presence of catalytic amounts of hafnium tetrachloride in a domestic microwave oven. The expected product was the addition of a cyanide group at the anomeric position of the glycal derivative. However, addition of cyanide to the anomeric center was not achieved by these reagent combinations. The study has identified a novel C-glucal disaccharide having nitrile at the anomeric centre of

one of the glucal moiety. In this communication we describe our novel findings.

Results and discussion

We initially focused to performed the carbon Ferrier rearrangement on 3,4,6-tri-O-acetyl-D-glucal (**1**) by using 1 equivalent of trimethyl silyl cyanide and catalytic amount of hafnium tetrachloride in anhydrous acetonitrile at 0°C for 1 h. However, under this condition we realized that the unusual product was formed, but substantial amount of starting material was recovered. The TLC profile of the reaction also showed complicated reaction. After careful repetition of the reaction with 0.5 equivalent of the catalyst in acetonitrile at 0°C for 2 h, reaction was completed. After quenching the reaction with aqueous NaHCO₃ resulted in isolation of an unusual product. Careful microanalysis of the sample showed the 3,1-dimer of the glucal with the nitrile functionality at the anomeric position. Glycals have been used as electrophilic partners in many of the processes notably via the carbon Ferrier rearrangement. Such work was carried out by Ferrier and Prasad who reported the dimer as 10% yield from the reaction of tri-O-acetyl-D-glucal (**1**) in presence of BF₃·OEt₂ as a promoter. Despite several attempts under conventional reaction conditions, the reaction profile remained complicated and formation of a complex reaction mixture along with poor yield of the unprecedented **1-3** C-glycoside with very poor anomeric selectivity (1:1) was observed (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Unprecedented C-glycosylation of the glycal under thermal condition.

We then turned to perform this reaction under microwave condition. The reaction was carried out with the automatic and domestic microwave reactor with 1 mmol of glycal derivatives and 0.5 mmol of hafnium tetrachloride as the promoter followed by trimethyl silyl cyanide as cyanide donor for the reaction. Surprisingly very clean reaction was observed under this condition with high degree of anomeric selectivity and excellent yield of the product was obtained in a short time. The result of the microwave irradiation condition is de-

Scheme 2. Unprecedented C-glycosylation of the glycal under microwave condition.

Table 1

Entry	R ¹	R ²	2a (α) + 2b (β) ^a		Time (min)	Yield (%)
			Anomeric ratio			
1	H	OAc	9	1	2	80
2	OAc	H	8	2	5	85

^aAnomeric ratio were calculated from ¹H NMR of the crude mixture.

^bIsolated yield after column chromatography.

lined in (Scheme 2).

The structure of the product suggests that glycal acts as a nucleophile that the process leads to the dimer. This is further confirmed by the fact that the disaccharide is found to be unsaturated as the process follows Ferrier type of rearrangement. Mechanistically, it can be explained via the loss of 3-O-acyl group to allylic oxocarbenium ion which then attacks the second molecule of the glycal to produce the another oxa-carbenium ion (Scheme 3)¹¹.

This may lead further oligomerization but the acetate groups prevent it. The external trimethyl silyl nitrile furnishes the very powerful nitrile nucleophile which preferentially traps the oxa-carbenium intermediate.

Formation of the alkenyl glycoside suggests that the anomeric oxygen of the glucal is really responsible for the migration of the double bond to the next available position and removal of the 3-acetoxy groups. This reaction has a similarity to our earlier observation in which we failed to produce any glycosides with galactose glucal or with glucose that are protected with poor leaving groups. It has been hypothesized that galactose glucal failed to produce glycoside because of the absence of anchimeric assistance in it. The stereochemistry of the 3-position of glucals derived from glucose and galactose is different. In glucose glucal, an anchimeric assistance is highly possible and therefore, oxonium ion can act in displacing the double bond and removing the 3-acetoxy group. The whole process is believed to occur through a concerted mechanism. The role of the protecting

Scheme 3. Proposed mechanism for dimerization of the glycal moiety.

group at the C-3 position of the glucal is therefore, highly crucial. In our earlier study, even glucal derived from glucose with ether protective groups failed to produce any glycosides. A similar observation was noted in this experiment. Following an identical procedure, benzylether glucose glucal failed to produce similar disaccharide under an identical reaction condition.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in a Fisher Scientific electrochemical Mel-Temp* manual melting point apparatus (Model 1001) equipped with a 300°C thermometer. FT-IR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Alpha modular Platinum-ATR FT-IR spectrometer with OPUS software, using the samples directly (neat) without making pellets. ¹H NMR (600 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (150 MHz) spectra were obtained at room temperature with Bruker superconducting Ultrashield™ Plus 600 MHz NMR spectrometer with central field 14.09 Tesla, coil inductance 89.1 Henry and magnetic energy 1127.2 kJ using CDCl₃ as solvent. Tri-O-acetyl-D-glucal (reagent grade, 98%) purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Corporation was used. All other chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Corporation (analytical grade). Throughout the project the solvents were purchased from Fisher-Scientific. Deionized water was used for the preparation of all aqueous solutions. The spectral data for the compound is as followed:

General experimental procedure for conventional reaction:

The D-glucal 100 mg (0.367 mmol) was dissolved in anhydrous dichloromethane followed by hafnium tetrachloride

10 mol% (0.036 mg) and 1.5 equivalent of freshly distilled TMSCN (0.07 mL) at room temperature. The reaction mixture was stirred at elevated temperatures for 1 h. The completion of the reaction was monitored by thin layer chromatography. The reaction mixture was cooled and quenched with 10% aqueous acetic acid. The organic layer was washed with deionized water, brine solution, and dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate. The solvent was evaporated under rotary evaporation and the crude mass was purified by flash column chromatography using 15% EtOAc and hexane solution affording the title compound **2a** as a colorless viscous liquid (90 mg, 90%); ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 2.12 (s, 2×3H), 2.13 (s, 2×3H), 3.88–3.82 (m, 2×1H), 4.31–4.10 (m, 2×1H), 5.40–5.29 (m, 2×2H), 5.48–5.54 (m, 2×1H), 5.86–5.29 (m, 2×1H), 5.97–5.90 (m, 2×1H); ¹³C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 20.74 (2×CH₃), 20.93 (2×CH₃), 62.53 (2×CH), 63.56 (2×CH₂), 69.05 (2×CH), 91.51 (2×OCH), 128.74 (2×CH), 129.70 (2×CH), 170.20 (2×CO), 170.70 (2×CO); IR ν_{max}: 1739.94 cm⁻¹ (C=O).

General experimental procedure for conventional reaction:

For microwave-irradiation method, acetonitrile was used as the solvent. Low power irradiation of the reaction mixture for 2 min afforded the product. The temperature of the reaction mixture was controlled by adjusting the on-off switch present in the microwave oven.

In a small microwave proof test tube, glycals (1 mmol) was taken with acetonitrile (1 mL), hafnium tetrachloride (0.5 mmol) and TMSCN (0.5 mL). The mixture was irradiated at 80°C for 2–5 min. The reaction mixture was diluted with

dichloromethane (10 mL), washed with water (2 mL), organic part was dried with sodium sulfate and solvent was evaporated. The crude product showed identical IR and NMR data with the compounds prepared earlier by conventional method.

Conclusion

We have studied hafnium tetrachloride-catalyzed trimethylsilyl cyanide-mediated glycosylation of a glucal derived from protected glucose under classical as well as under microwave method. The results obtained herein can be useful for the preparation of novel carbohydrates through glucal-glucal hetero coupling reaction. The results obtained herein are new and clearly deserve further study in this area. Further study on this unique observation with various D-glucal and galactal derivatives is currently under investigation and will be reported in due course.

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